

Night Image Enhancement by means of Retinex Filtering

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Abstract This is the fourth work of a series which is showing applications of Retinex filters. In the first paper, we considered the images from microscopes. In the second, we discussed how a Retinex filtering can help us in the investigation of the motion of sand dunes. In the third, underwater images have been considered. Here we give examples concerning images that can be obtained by night photography. The filter that we use is the GIMP Retinex, based on the original Retinex method developed by Fabien Pelisson.

Keywords Night image enhancement, Image processing, Retinex Filters.

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The Retinex methods for image processing have been developed according to some experimental observations. These experiments concern the fact that it is easy to find discrepancies between an image that we have recorded by a camera and the real scene that we have observed. The reason is the following: humans are able to see details both in the shadows and in the nearby illuminated areas, whereas a photograph of the same scene is showing either the shadows as too dark or the bright areas as overexposed [1].

Using as a model the peculiar features of the human vision, which are quite different from those of the recording devices [1-3], several algorithms of image processing have been developed to simulate the human ability of adapting to adverse conditions. These algorithms are known as Retinex algorithms. The first of them was conceived by Edwin H. Land, an American scientist and inventor, best known as co-founder of Polaroid Corporation. As explained in Ref.1, through the years, Land made several models, until the last that he proposed in 1986. The term “Retinex” was coined by Land himself, combining the words “retina” and “cortex”, to indicate the results of his researches. They tell that the human colour perception is involving all levels of vision processes, from the retina to the cerebral cortex.

Several Retinex approaches exist [1-9]: the single-scale Retinex (SSR), the multiscale Retinex (MSR), and, for colour images, the MultiScale Retinex with Colour Restoration (MSRCR). Among MSRCR we find the GIMP Retinex, a freely available filter originally developed by Fabien Pelisson [10]. The resulting image of this filter can be adjusted selecting different levels, scales and dynamics. In particular, three “levels” exist. The “uniform” level tends to process both low and high intensity areas fairly; the “low” level “flares up” the lower intensity areas on the image; the “high” level tends to “bury” the lower intensity areas in favor of a better rendering of the clearer areas of the image.

In some previous works [11-18], we have proposed several examples of the use of the Retinex filter provided by GIMP. Originally, the filter has been developed by Fabien Pelisson. As we have shown, the GIMP tool is suitable for enhancing the images recorded in foggy conditions and in night scenes, and in the processing of underwater images. Here, in the fourth paper of a series which is discussing the applications of Retinex filters, we consider the case again of the enhancement of the night scenes. In the first paper of the series we discussed imagery from microscopes [19], and in the second we have shown how the GIMP Retinex filtering can help

in the investigation of the motion of sand dunes [20]. In the third, underwater images have been considered [21].

Here in the following, several examples of night scenes. From them we can clearly see the effect of the Retinex filtering and the results, in term of evidencing details in the recorded scenes, that we can obtain. On the left, the original images are given, on the right the results of the filtering. Images are from the web site <https://www.piqsels.com/> , license to use Creative Commons Zero - CC0.

Fig.1 - <https://www.piqsels.com/en/public-domain-photo-zbrwn>

Fig.2 - <https://www.piqsels.com/en/public-domain-photo-skjdb>

Fig.3 - Historical city of Prague at night - <https://www.piqsels.com/en/public-domain-photo-zktes>

Fig.4 - <https://www.piqsels.com/en/public-domain-photo-zktyo>

Fig.5 - <https://www.piqsels.com/en/public-domain-photo-zbztq>

Fig.6 - <https://www.piqsels.com/en/public-domain-photo-sklms>

Fig.7 - <https://www.piqsels.com/en/public-domain-photo-skjji>

Fig.8 - <https://www.piqsels.com/en/public-domain-photo-zhvif>

Fig.9 - <https://www.piqsels.com/en/public-domain-photo-zqchs>

Fig.10 - <https://www.piqsels.com/en/public-domain-photo-zxbtl>

Fig.11 - <https://www.piqsels.com/en/public-domain-photo-zkkjt>

Fig.12 - <https://www.piqsels.com/en/public-domain-photo-zdrbq>

Fig.13 - <https://www.piqsels.com/en/public-domain-photo-fusep>

Fig.14 - <https://www.piqsels.com/en/public-domain-photo-smkve>

Fig.15 - <https://www.piqsels.com/en/public-domain-photo-fvbai>

Fig.16 - <https://www.piqsels.com/en/public-domain-photo-fvbeg>

Fig.17 - <https://www.piqsels.com/en/public-domain-photo-fsprn>

Fig.18 - <https://www.piqsels.com/en/public-domain-photo-svnow>

Fig.19 - <https://www.piqsels.com/en/public-domain-photo-fsfb>

References

- [1] Barnard, K., & Funt, B. (1999). Investigations into multi-scale Retinex, in *Colour Imaging: Vision and Technology*, L. MacDonald, Ed. and M. Ronnier Luo. Ed., John Wiley and Sons, pp. 9-17. ISBN: 9780471985310
- [2] Zhixi Bian, & Yan Zhang (2002). Retinex image enhancement techniques: Algorithm, application and advantages, EE264 final project report for Image Processing and Reconstruction.
- [3] Jobson, D.J., Rahman, Z., & Woodell, G.A. (1997). A Multi-Scale Retinex for bridging the gap between colour images and the human observation of scenes, *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing* 6(7):965-976. DOI: 10.1109/83.597272
- [4] Land, E.H. (1986). An alternative technique for the computation of the designator in the Retinex theory of color vision, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.* 83:3078-3080. PMID: PMC323455

- [5] Land, E.H. (1983). Recent advances in Retinex theory and some implications for cortical computations, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.* 80:5163-5169. PMID: PMC384211
- [6] Land, E. H. (1986). Recent advances in Retinex theory, *Vis. Res.* 26:7-21. DOI: 10.1016/0042-6989(86)90067-2
- [7] Land, E. H. (1959). Experiments in color vision, *Scientific American*, May Issue, 285-298.
- [8] Land, E. H. (1959). Color vision and the natural image, *Proc. of the National Academy of Sciences* 45(1):115–129. PMID: PMC222521
- [9] Jobson, J., Rahman, Z., & Woodell, G.A. (1997). Properties and performance of a center/surround Retinex, *Image Processing IEEE Transactions on* 6(3):451-462. DOI: 10.1109/83.557356
- [10] Fabien Pelisson, GIMP Retinex, <http://www-prima.inrialpes.fr/pelisson/MSRCR.php>
- [11] Sparavigna, A. C. (2015). Retinex filtering and thresholding of foggy images. PHILICA.COM Article number 511.
- [12] Sparavigna, A. C., & Marazzato, R. (2015). Effects of GIMP Retinex Filtering Evaluated by the Image Entropy. arXiv preprint arXiv:1512.05653.
- [13] Marazzato, R., & Sparavigna, A. C. (2015). Retinex filtering of foggy images: generation of a bulk set with selection and ranking. arXiv preprint arXiv:1509.08715.
- [14] Sparavigna, A. C., & Marazzato, R. (2016). Evaluation of GIMP Retinex Filtering of Images by Means of the Shen++Max Shannon Entropy Finder. <hal-01308434>
- [15] Sparavigna, A. C. (2015). GIMP Retinex for enhancing images from microscopes. *International Journal of Sciences*, 4(6), 72-79. DOI: 10.18483/ijsci.758
- [16] Sparavigna, A. C. (2015). An image processing approach based on Gnu Image Manipulation Program GIMP to the panoramic radiography. *International Journal of Sciences*, 4(5), 57-67. DOI: 10.18483/ijsci.721
- [17] Sparavigna, A. C., & Marazzato, R. (2017). The GIMP Retinex Filter Applied to the Fabric Fault Detection. *International Journal of Sciences*, 6(03), 106-112. DOI: 10.18483/ijSci.1227
- [18] Sparavigna, A. C. (2017). GIMP Retinex and Underwater Imaging. 2017. <hal-01507308>
- [19] Sparavigna, A. C. (2019, December 1). Applying Retinex Filters to Microscopic Images. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3559088>
- [20] Sparavigna, A. C. (2020, May 2). Satellite Images of Sand Dunes Filtered by Means of GIMP Retinex. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3782537>
- [21] Sparavigna, A. C. (2020, June 9). Retinex Filtering of Underwater Images. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.388641>